

D1.1: Stakeholder engagement methodology and plan

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission

Authors: Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland, Kseniia Makhortova, Leif Martin Hokstad (NTNU)

Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA)

Harriet Bartlett, Maëlle Quevillard (XR4EUROPE)

Editors: Rigmor Baraas, Rose Bernabe (USN)

Project title: The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project

Project acronym: XR4Human

Grant Agreement no.: 101070155

Lead contractor for this deliverable:

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101070155
Project Acronym:	XR4Human
Project Title:	The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project
Title of Deliverable:	D1.1 Stakeholder engagement methodology and plan
Work Package:	WP 1
Due date according to contract:	31 January 2023
Editor(s):	Rigmor Baraas and Rose Bernabe (USN)
Contributor(s):	Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland, Kseniia Makhortova, Leif Martin Hokstad (NTNU), Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA), Harriet Bartlett and Maëlle Quevillard (XR4EUROPE).
Reviewer(s):	Faisal Mushtaq (UoL), Rigmor Baraas and Rose Bernabe (USN)
Approved by	Rosemarie Bernabe (UiO/USN), Rigmor Baraas (USN)

ABSTRACT:	This report presents a comprehensive overview of stakeholder engagement. It considers the initial analysis and definitions of concepts and differences in stakeholder groups, suggests ways to identify the right approach, and reveals the main existing models of stakeholder engagement. The report suggests supplementing and strengthening stakeholder engagement with the theory on communities and their lifecycle. Based on on this and in combination with an understanding of the stakeholder groups and communities relevant for the XR4HUMAN project—a targeted XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement methodology is suggested.
------------------	---

Keyword List:	Stakeholder engagement, Communities of interest

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I OSLOST-NORGE	USN	NO
2.	Partner	XR4EUROPE	XR4Europe	BE
3.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	NO
4.	Partner	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
5.	Partner	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	NTNU	NO
6.	Partner	UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	ULEI	NL
7.	Partner	KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE	KIT	DE
8.	Partner	INSTITUTT FOR ENERGITEKNIKK	IFE	NO
9.	Partner	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Fraunhofer	DE
10.	Partner	OPEN AR CLOUD EUROPE GEMEINNUTZIGE UG	OARC EU	DE
11.	Partner	STICHTING FONTYS	Fontys	NL
12.	AP	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UNIVLEEDS	UK

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	17.01.2023	Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland, Kseniia Makhortova, Leif Martin Hokstad (NTNU), Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA), Harriet Bartlett and Maëlle Quevillard (XR4EUROPE).	Preparation of 1st draft
0.2	20.01.2023	Faisal Mushtaq	Review of 1st draft
0.3	25.01.2023	Harriet Bartlett	Edit of 2nd draft
1.0	29.01.2023	Rigmor Baraas and Rose Bernabe	Preparation of final version

Table of contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Stakeholder engagement: literature review	6
2.1	From past to present	7
2.2	Components of Stakeholder Engagement	8
2.3	Contents of Stakeholder Engagement	9
2.4	Stakeholder identification and analysis	10
2.5	Developing a Stakeholder Engagement Plan	11
2.6	Six Steps Stakeholder Engagement Plan	11
2.7	The International Association for Public Participation Stakeholder Engagement Method	12
2.8	Good Faith Stakeholder Engagement Method	13
3	Communities of Interest (Col) and community methodology: an overview	16
3.1	Charting the community landscape	17
3.2	Communities of interest (Col)	17
3.3	Framework for characterizing communities: domain, network, practice	19
3.4	Seven Principles for Cultivating a Community	21
4	Towards XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement methodology	22
4.1	Identifying Principles for Cultivating a Community of XR4HUMAN Stakeholders	22
4.1.1	Choosing the engagement approach	22
4.1.2	From ignorance to creativity	23
4.2	XR4Human Stakeholder Engagement methodology	24
4.3	XR4Human Stakeholder Engagement methodology	29
4.3.1	Building a strong XR4HUMAN Stakeholder database and analysis	29
4.3.2	XR4HUMAN Encounters and stakeholder engagement activities	30
4.3.2.1	The Website	34
4.3.2.2	The Forum	34
4.3.2.3	Working Groups	35
4.3.2.4	Participating in conferences and events	36
4.3.2.5	Organisation of final conference	39
4.3.2.6	Legacy	39
5	Conclusion: towards XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement methodology	40
5.1	Summary: XR4HUMAN Stakeholder Engagement Methodology	40
5.2	Risk factors and limitations: Monitoring stakeholder communities from a SWOT perspective.	41
6	REFERENCES	43
7	APPENDICES	49

Introduction

The main goal of the XR4HUMAN project is the creation of European standards for XR supporting an ethical and human-centered development process for hardware and software manufacturers, through tight collaboration and interaction with industry, consumers, regulators and academia. XR4HUMAN also seeks to empower the end-users, supporting inclusivity and availability, ensuring that every European company and citizen is benefiting from and has access to XR technologies, making a field for a strong and competitive ecosystem whilst building public trust and acceptance.

XR4HUMAN is dedicated to meaningful, productive, comprehensive and inclusive stakeholder engagement in project design and implementation. Efficient stakeholder engagement is an essential milestone in achieving sustainable and ethical development. Industry and Developers associations, Consumer Associations, Civil society organizations, General public, Research Policy makers, Legal experts, content developers, Members of Research Ethics Councils, Science journalists and other key stakeholders are essential partners in promoting the development of new ethical, inclusive, democratic sustainable standards for the use of XR technologies and the related security, privacy, data protection, technical and ethical alignment challenges.

Ethical and comprehensive stakeholder engagement is integral to realizing the overarching goals of the XR4HUMAN project and aims to:

- Provide meaningful access to dialogue and decision-making at all stages of the project development
- Enhance the results of development through effective partnerships
- Define stakeholder priorities in order to better tailor project activities, opportunities and benefits
- Strive to ensure that no one is excluded and that vulnerable project stakeholders have a voice in project design and implementation
- Identify potential limitations and conflicts that may impact on the effectiveness of the project
- Ensure transparency, accountability, and integrity
- Examine and incorporate local knowledge to improve project design, along with avoidance and mitigation of project-related risks and impacts
- Provide a feedback and monitoring framework to ensure that the project is achieving its intended results and identifying potential unforeseen consequences

The XR4HUMAN stakeholders are identified as follows in the XR4HUMAN proposal:

- Associations of industries and Developers (Business Europe, Digital Europe, Eurochambres)
- Research Policy makers (e.g. EC officials, members of CEI)
- Legal experts (e.g. members of STOA)
- Researchers and programmers (e.g. immersive healthcare collaboration)
- Members of RECs (e.g. members of EUREC)
- Science journalists (working in e-journals, e.g. Horizon Magazine)
- Users of XR technologies
- Lay people with no knowledge or experience in using XR technologies

The goal of this deliverable is to create a methodology for identifying and engaging different stakeholder groups and communities, including representatives from companies, users, citizens (including individuals who are using or are familiar with the capabilities of extended reality technologies, as well as people who have no experience nor knowledge in this technological area), public bodies and researchers. In order to develop such a methodology, the deliverable

- 1) provides a review and analysis of stakeholder engagement literature and existing methodologies relevant for XR4HUMAN (chapter 2)
- 2) provides an introduction to the topic of communities of interest and a methodology for seeding and empowering such communities, including the methodology for transformation of “symmetry of ignorance” into creative partnerships (chapter 3);
- 3) suggests an eclectic 7 step model of Stakeholder engagement specifically generated for XR4HUMAN based on 1) and 2) in chapter 4.1 and 4.2
- 4) provides a concrete roadmap/plan of XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement activities based on 3) in chapter 4.3
- 5) summarizes the outcomes of this deliverable and presents a SWOT analysis in chapter 5.

1 Stakeholder engagement: literature review

Following XR4HUMAN’s main objective of supporting the co-creation of ethical policies and regulations within the XR field, it is important to consider the diversity and different involvement levels of different stakeholders in the use of XR technologies. Further, to ensure comprehensive, inclusive and democratic participation of stakeholder groups in the project it is important to correctly identify these groups and decide on a suitable engagement model. The chosen model needs to ensure engagement,

collaboration and partnership within and during the project as well as dissemination of ethical standards for the use of XR technologies after the completion of the project. Based on this objective a review and analysis of the existing scientific literature related to stakeholder engagement in the technology and business sectors was conducted. Reflections around existing knowledge and experience included in the theoretical framework on stakeholder identification and engagement makes the foundation for the successful implementation of the XR4HUMAN project.

To implement comprehensive and accurate research in the Stakeholder engagement area, the following questions were asked:

- What is Stakeholder engagement?
- What kinds of stakeholder-engagement approaches exist and will provide successful implementation of comprehensive stakeholder engagement?

Moreover, to highlight the most important parts of stakeholder engagement:

- How to define components and contents of stakeholder engagement?
- Turning to the more practical and design-inspired part: which approach may suit the needs of XR4HUMAN best?

To respond to these questions, a literature review on stakeholder engagement was conducted. For this deliverable, the widely known definition of “stakeholders as individuals, groups, or organizations that affect or are affected by organizational activities” was used (Freeman, 1984). The focus was on the following two main fields of stakeholder engagement: (a) business and society, and (b) management and strategy, both connected to accepting and working with new technologies.

1.1 From past to present

Research on stakeholder engagement appeared in the peer-reviewed papers in the 1990s (Coff, 1999) and stakeholder engagement as a concept started to gain prominence in business-oriented literature at the beginning of the 2000s (Andriof, 2002). The key objective of the construct was to identify the difference between the “one-sided management of stakeholders”, “enhancing shareholder value” and “engaging stakeholders for long-term value creation” (Andriof, 2002). Stakeholder theory places stakeholders at the center of strategic thinking and defines relationships with stakeholders as the purpose of analysis (Freeman, 1984). As stakeholder theory has focused on understanding the interaction and relationships between organizations and their stakeholders (Andriof, 2002), stakeholder engagement research is a natural and logical continuation of this theory. Usually, this research direction assess practical implementation of stakeholder theory (Greenwood, 2007).

Previous research in the business, society, management and strategy literature focus on similar issues. This include the relationship between CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) and stakeholder engagement (Kujala, 2022), the moral dimension of stakeholder engagement (Calton, 2006), organizational legitimacy (Scholz, 2019), responsible leadership (Patzner, 2018) and deliberative democracy (Dawkins, 2021). Current research is becoming more directed towards innovation (Watson, 2020) and entrepreneurship (Sachs, 2021).

The XR4HUMAN project focuses on engaging different stakeholder groups to work with and create ethical guidelines for the use, development and interoperability of XR technologies. A comprehensive analysis and consideration of stakeholder engagement from different perspectives, going beyond technological and social experience, taking into account industry and governance, will be essential for creating inclusive ethical guidelines of engagement in the field of XR technologies.

1.2 Components of Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement theory definitions diverge and emphasize different aspects. Based on the reviewed literature, stakeholder engagement entails a moral component. Stakeholder engagement is ethical if the organization has positive and sincere motives and/or the relationship is honest and consensual (Kujala, 2022). Some scholars believe that stakeholder engagement is morally positive if it implies acceptance and consideration (Noland, 2010), stakeholder empowerment (Ghodsvali, 2019), or consideration of stakeholder desires, demands, and possibilities (Todeschini, 2020). Moreover, as the use of the stakeholder framework itself is a kind of sign of an understanding of actions as ethical actions (Purnell, 2012), the literature on stakeholder engagement often refers implicitly to the moral component.

Despite the ethical aspect, stakeholder engagement has a strategic and pragmatic component (Dmitriev, 2021). Stakeholder theory is initially a topic of strategic management (Freeman, 1984), and the strategic aspect of stakeholder engagement focuses on the willingness of stakeholders to contribute to the value creation of business. Generally, engagement is grounded in the input of resources to improve various results, such as productivity, reputation, or competitive edge (Barney, 2018). Furthermore, quantitative stakeholder research has mainly been focused on verifying the preconditions of empirical stakeholder theory, which argues that a firm's stakeholder orientation has a positive effect on its financial performance (Ayuso, 2014).

Consequently, based on the important points of stakeholder engagement and considering the XR4HUMAN project community including Industry and Developers associations, Consumer Associations, Civil society organizations, General public, Research Policy makers, Legal experts, content developers, Members of Research Ethics Councils, Science journalists and public users of XR technologies it is important to take these factors into account. Issues related to ethical use should be prioritised as this is

consistent with the main objective of the XR4HUMAN project, the creation of ethical norms for the use of XR technologies. However, it is worth considering the needs of the European XR industry, which will be directly affected by evolving ethical guidelines, affecting the production process and development of hardware and software. As well as interoperability issues, where it is important to consider inclusive rules for creating and working with applications.

The practical elements of stakeholder engagement theory relate to pragmatism as a philosophical orientation (Dmitriev, 2021), address action and problem solving in practical contexts (Freeman, 1984), and emphasize the practical implications of actions aimed at improving stakeholder lifestyles (Voparil, 2010). Therefore, recognizing different stakeholder groups and measuring the practical implications of stakeholder interactions are essential components of the pragmatic approach. It indicates how stakeholder interaction operates in the social and natural environment and considers what actions may be appropriate in a particular context and case (Sandberg, 2010). The pragmatic component of stakeholder engagement addresses the timing aspect, including temporal processes with a starting point and an endpoint, as well as the continuous manner of stakeholder engagement.

Most of the existing definitions focus on moral, strategic, and practical components of stakeholder engagement. These components show the diversity and versatility of the stakeholder engagement concept. The moral component emphasizes the morally positive impact of stakeholder engagement through moral conduct and inclusive stakeholder engagement, whereas the strategic component underlines instrumental engagement and reciprocal economic advantages (Kujala, 2022). The pragmatic component, by its integrative nature, is in the middle, combining the strategic and moral views for joint value creation and for achieving the main goals of the project, XR4HUMAN seeks to follow the pragmatic view when engaging with the stakeholders.

1.3 Contents of Stakeholder Engagement

Reviewed literature points out that it is an intentional activity with explicit or implicit aims linked to participants' interests (Nalick, 2016). In addition to the term 'aims', stakeholder engagement research also uses 'purpose' (Viglia, 2018), 'reasons' (Shackleton, 2019), and 'incentives' (Miska, 2014). According to O'Riordan and Fairbrass (O'Riordan, 2014) stakeholder "engagement refers to a variety of activities that enable dialogue between an organization and its stakeholders". The literature uses a variety of terms referring to stakeholder engagement activities, such as mechanisms (Pucci, 2020), levels (Mitter, 2019), strategies (Herremans, 2016), methods (Shackleton, 2019), steps (Novoa, 2018), forms (Viglia, 2018), interventions (Watson, 2020), approaches (Shackleton, 2019), types (Jolibert, 2012) and degrees (Mitter, 2019). Usually, this way in literature is describing one-way activities, such as informing stakeholders, or mutual and reciprocal two-way activities.

The impacts of stakeholder engagement refer most often to an improved competitive advantage or social and ecological well-being and concern the participating stakeholders and beyond (Dawkins, 2021). Common impacts illustrate the intended or unintended changes that follow the process of stakeholder engagement.

1.4 Stakeholder identification and analysis

Before developing a stakeholder engagement plan, it is necessary to identify key stakeholders and affected social groups and organizations. Different methods of stakeholder identification and analysis are considered in the theory literature. These practices concentrate on the interconnections of groups or institutions with respect to their interests or effects on policy in the wider political, economic, and cultural landscape. Such methods also enable analysts to develop an awareness of the power, influence, needs, and conflicts of interest of stakeholders (Bryson, 2004). Stakeholder analysis informs the development of a stakeholder engagement plan for a project and helps prioritize interventions to engage with specific stakeholder groups and individuals (UNDP, 2020).

Stakeholder analysis seeks answers to the following fundamental questions:

- Who are the key stakeholders of the proposed project?
- What are the interests of these stakeholders related to the project?
- How will stakeholders' interests be affected (positively/negatively) by the project?
- Which stakeholders are the most vulnerable and subject to potential adverse impacts?
- Which stakeholders wield the most influence to affect project outcomes?
- Whose capacity needs to be supported to enable them to participate?

Based on the findings of the stakeholder analysis, for successful project implementation and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of interest and engagement, it is worth using the below 4-quadrant diagram to match specific stakeholders with their perspectives. This process is illustrated in **Fig. 2 Influence/Interest Matrix (Mendelow, 1991) (see appendix 1)**.

A systematic approach is needed to ensure that all potential stakeholders are identified, and their interests well understood so that they will be appropriately engaged throughout the project (UNDP, 2020). Stakeholder analysis typically involves three main steps: (1) identifying stakeholders, (2) specifying stakeholder interests and mapping power relations and influence, and (3) prioritizing engagement across different stakeholder groups.

1.5 Developing a Stakeholder Engagement Plan

First, it is worth noting that no one type, or format of stakeholder engagement plan will be appropriate for all projects. The content will depend on several variables, such as the character, scope, size, location, and duration of the project; the range of stakeholder interests; the extent of potential positive and negative impacts on people and the environment; and the potential for misunderstandings and conflicts. For small projects with few potentially adverse social and environmental consequences or initial stakeholder concerns (e.g., a low-risk or simple, moderate-risk project), a "simplified" stakeholder engagement plan can be used, focusing primarily on initial consultation, disclosure, and periodic reporting (Harrison, 2013). More complex projects with potentially significant detrimental social and environmental outcomes (e.g., complex projects with moderate risk, projects with significant/high risk) necessitate a more comprehensive plan for stakeholder engagement. A "comprehensive" design will specify processes for accessing full project information, good communication (Harclerode, 2016), and for undertaking iterative advisory and possibly consent processes during the social and environmental assessment process, development of mitigation and management plans, project implementation monitoring, and evaluation.

A stakeholder engagement plan for XR4HUMAN is presented in Chapter 4 of this deliverable.

Regardless of the complexity and other details of the project, the stakeholder information listed in Figure 3 must be obtained before developing a stakeholder engagement plan (UNDP, 2020). Section 4.2 will further develop this from a practical perspective. **Figure 3. Stakeholder information must be obtained prior to the development of a stakeholder engagement plan (See appendix 2).**

Prior to project appraisal, a validation workshop should be held with stakeholders in addition to confirming the project's planned activities. It should also include review and agreement of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (UNDP, 2020). With the start of project implementation, an inception workshop should be held to assist project partners to understand the approved project design, understand their role and responsibilities in the project including stakeholder engagement during project implementation and monitoring, including communications, reporting, and conflict resolution and grievance redress.

1.6 Six Steps Stakeholder Engagement Plan

After conducting a comprehensive stakeholder analysis and identifying the key powerful and most vulnerable groups, as well as determining an engagement design that fits the objectives of the required project, it is worthwhile to focus on the stakeholder engagement plan directly.

The comprehensive engagement should be structured in a way that enables the perspectives of the diverse Stakeholders to be considered, to cover the interests of the most influential and less affected or interested in the project development. (Hine, 2009). It is not practical nor relevant to engage all identified Stakeholder groups on the same level of intensity, using the same approach. It is important to carefully select Stakeholders for ongoing consultation and collaboration because being strategic and clear about whom to engage with – and why – can help save both time and money. Moreover, it will help better manage the expectations of the Stakeholders. When Stakeholder groups are consulted and express opinions, only to find no action taken to respond to their requests and needs, this can significantly undermine the perceived value of the procedure and negatively impact trust and reputation (Legacy, 2010).

Thus, considering all the previously presented material, it is worth looking at one of the most common classic models of stakeholder engagement used in the business literature. It consists of six major steps and covers the needs of a variety of stakeholder groups, while the procedures, depending on the level of involvement and influence of stakeholders, are determined in the next step by the chosen plan's implementation technique (**Table 3, see appendix 3**) (Cochrane, 2017).

However, the art of Stakeholder engagement does not rest on which technique is chosen, but on how well the technique is matched to the stakeholders' profile, the situation and the specific issue/challenge they face. To sum up, the recommendations from the reviewed literature on the correlation between all main components of stakeholder engagement, it is important to point to the main advice: to focus on the final step - technique (**Table 4, see appendix 3**). In the process of choosing the technique, it is necessary to provide a comprehensive method of communicating and considering the inputs received from stakeholder groups so that everyone feels and understands that their interests are considered. This creates a feeling of ownership about the outcomes of the project and increases the interest of Stakeholders to provide their needed views/opinions for the project (Herremans, 2016). The successful completion of a project usually depends on how the Stakeholders view it. Their requirements, expectations, perceptions, personal agendas, and concerns will influence the project, shape what success looks like, and impact the outcomes that can be achieved.

1.7 The International Association for Public Participation Stakeholder Engagement Method

Stakeholder engagement methods are how stakeholder's views and opinions are elicited, or by which stakeholders are involved in decision-making. Engagement can take various forms. The International Association for Public Participation identified five levels of stakeholder engagement: (EU, 2014)(Table 5). This version of the table is eclectically updated to the specific features of the XR4HUMAN project (**see appendix 4**).

In considering this approach for engaging XR4HUMAN stakeholders, particular attention has been paid to the emphasis on engagement and collaboration to help overcome misunderstandings, symmetry of ignorance (as elaborated in chapter 3, and to ensure a comparable level of commitment to the project. These points are very important in working with stakeholders, which include groups from the public to software developers, from the administrative office to bloggers. Working together on project goals and the empowerment of end-users opens the possibility for everyone to communicate their value and create a sustainable long-term partnership.

1.8 Good Faith Stakeholder Engagement Method

The good faith principle derives from the Latin term “bona fides”, meaning honest and sincere intention, and is now a moral matter that can only be answered by clarifying one's idea of honesty and, in many cases, deciding what standards of behaviours are reasonable (Mather, 2002). Research in the mid-2010s suggested a methodology for stakeholder engagement based on the core ethical guidelines that constitute a minimum in the business sphere, three of which overlap with the principle of integrity (Dawnkins, 2013). First, respect is necessary for mutually beneficial collaboration. Second, integrity is essential to the effective operation of markets, and third, respect for autonomy acknowledges that people are entitled to freedom, without which contracts would not be morally binding. (Quinn, 1995).

Such principles form a conscientious approach that encourages interaction, while preserving individual autonomy to pursue self-interest, which is integral to free markets. Regulation tends to be retrospective, and it is often the case that no corporations or stakeholders are happy with the outcome. The fundamental elements of good faith, however, are that the parties really want to negotiate and that they do not make false claims (Gaal, 1987). The most classic definition of good faith emphasizes that while the law cannot force parties to be unbiased, it can at least force them to behave as if they are trying to persuade and want to be persuaded (Cox, 1958). One would expect good faith stakeholder interaction to have similar aspects of dialogue and negotiation.

The main principles of stakeholder engagement using the good faith approach are illustrated **in Table 6 (see appendix 5)**.

In sum, good faith stakeholder engagement is a substantive form of input that provides a better mutual understanding of key partners and stakeholders such that either side can prevail in a dispute, provides an inclusive forum for participation, and prevents either party from being dependent solely on the benevolence of the other (Dawnkins, 2013).

While considering the Good Faith stakeholder engagement approach for the XR4HUMAN project, the focus has been on emphasizing the ethical dimension of engagement. When a project focuses on creating inclusive ethical norms for the use of XR technologies, the engagement process itself must follow the same rules and follow an inclusive and fair stakeholder engagement policy. Considering the diversity of stakeholder engagement and influence, honest and open interaction, mutual respect, and trust in the organizers and among key stakeholders is a bond, a guarantee of long-term work and a trusting partnership. We believe that good faith engagement becomes more a prevalent aspect of stakeholder relations, corporations that adhere to its principles might achieve both ethical and competitive advantage with their stakeholders.

2.9 UNEP's Stakeholder Engagement plan

In 2005, the UN Environment Program released its stakeholder engagement plan. It is based on the Rules of Procedure of the United Nations Environment Assembly of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEA). Many existing stakeholder engagement plans and strategies are based on this model. In a clear and simple, yet comprehensive way, all the key points of a successful stakeholder engagement strategy are addressed, as well as its applicability to various stakeholder groups. **Fig. 7 (see appendix 6).**

The five-step process is structured to support thorough planning, preparation, action, and evaluation of every engagement activity. The process is a dynamic and ongoing cycle, which supports a comprehensive approach to engagement that over time is expected to contribute to an evidence-based platform for continuous improvement. **Table 8 (see appendix 7).**

How this process is applied will be driven by the purpose, level and type of engagement undertaken. It is also important to note that the process will operate at the strategic and operational ends of stakeholder engagement activities. It is possible to work on more than one step in the process at any time, with different stakeholders, depending on the nature of the engagement.

The suggested approach for stakeholder engagement in XR4HUMAN (as outlined in Chapter 4) has focused on strengthening the stakeholders involved and their level of exposure and vulnerability in the project. For a multi-stakeholder project like XR4HUMAN, this is reflected in the different ways in which different stakeholders interact and engage, and the importance of common collaboration and co-design platforms.

2.10 Discussion on the existing stakeholder engagement models

This chapter reviews the major, most popular modern models of stakeholder engagement, selected from relevant sources. These models have their own histories of creation and application,

successful experiences of implementation and drawbacks, when applied to other projects. For an inclusive and comprehensive fulfillment of the XR4HUMAN project objectives, it is necessary to choose the methodology that will identify the key, most vulnerable and most distant communities of the project objectives, as well as to responsibly choose the approach to stakeholder engagement. Furthermore, the chosen methodology needs to address both the first phase of the stakeholder engagement process, and provide a long-term plan for keeping stakeholders involved in the further development of safe, ethical, and inclusive XR in Europe. Versatility and extensiveness of the opportunities provided by each model needs to be balanced with advantages and disadvantages of each of the presented models, to fully consider the options for using them.

The UNEP model appears creative and versatile in terms of the choice of methods and ways to apply them. However, this approach does not address the particularities of the diversity of stakeholders and the need for an inclusive and targeted way of addressing them, since the same methods will not work for everyone. This model covers the initial involvement of stakeholders and interaction with them, but it lacks a plan for further work and building long-term cooperation with stakeholders.

The approach of the Good Faith model appears useful in terms of creating an ethical and inclusive project in any field. After all, having trusting and long-term relationships with stakeholders makes it possible to create the conditions for the active and inclusive participation of communities. However, the very mechanism of initial and widespread stakeholder engagement at all stages of project implementation is lacking, because the methodologies for dealing with stakeholder groups focus only on working internally with existing communities. The model does not include how to engage and expand the involvement of new participants.

The International Association for Public Participation stakeholder engagement model, contains an extensive and variable set of methods and approaches for performing community involvement in the project. The diversity of stakeholders and differences in approaches and tools for their involvement escapes the attention of the model, and the model focuses only on the initial phase of the project. After the strengthening phase, the model lacks suggestions for the transformation that will be inevitable in any project and the stakeholders involved in it.

The versatile and detailed Six-Step Model captures all the basic steps and elements required to successfully engage communities in a project. These steps must be addressed and followed at all stages of the engagement process. However, it is worth supplementing this model with elements of the importance of obtaining feedback from stakeholders and engaging diverse groups to ensure inclusive and ethical project execution.

After assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the described models, we conclude that ethical, inclusive, sustainable stakeholder engagement will require an eclectic approach to stakeholder engagement. An approach that combines the theoretical underpinnings from different models will be proposed for the XR4HUMAN project. In developing a new comprehensive methodology, we will adapt existing models and enhance the concept with specific techniques for reaching different stakeholder groups to ensure the democratic participation of all parties. The adopted methodology will also include a long-term plan for stakeholder involvement, building on the awareness of the different phases of community lifecycle.

Such awareness requires in turn a deeper understanding of the basic principles for seeding and nurturing communities of interest. We will use the Seven Principles for Cultivating a Community model suggested by Wenger, McDermott and Snyder (Wenger, 2002). This model can be taken as a starting point for developing a stakeholder management plan that will work with diverse communities to engage, support and monitor the community setting at all stages of the stakeholder groups' work with the project. By integrating and adapting the existing community models, the XR4HUMAN project will be able to support communities of XR4HUMAN stakeholders at all phases of project life and implementation. This to establish trustful, long-term relationships between decision-making actors, and to provide access to information, collaborative work, and horizons of the project transformation for all participants. Therefore, in this deliverable, in addition to stakeholder engagement related work, we introduce the literature on community methodology in the next chapter.

2 Communities of Interest (CoI) and community methodology: an overview

In the XR4HUMAN project we align the stakeholder analysis (the what) with a methodology for creating and nurturing stakeholders into communities of interest (the how), to better reach the goals of the XR4HUMAN project. Examples of determined goals include to increase the interest in and

engagement of key project stakeholders, provide meaningful access to dialogue and decision-making at all stages of the project development and enhance the results of development through effective partnerships (the why). By understanding and utilizing the research-based knowledge on communities and networks, a solidly founded methodology may be achieved.

2.1 Charting the community landscape

The notion of community has become increasingly important inside and among organizations and individuals of organizations. The informality of these communities seems suited to develop, to nourish and to pass on knowledge and attitudes within a knowledge domain. The literature consulted also suggests that organizations depend on the informal relationships inside and amongst organizations. For XR4HUMAN, we briefly illustrate various community possibilities, as this is described in the literature consulted, and focus further on 'Communities of Interest' as most relevant for XR4HUMAN context. A typology of relevant community is provided by Fisher et al. (Fischer, G., Rohde, M., & Wulf, V. (2007).:

- Communities of practice: "groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and can learn how to do it better as they interact regularly." (CoP (Wenger 1991, Wegner 1998)
- Networks of practice (NoP); people across organizations who share practices and information, but do not work in the same organization.
- Community of interests (CoI): gather in the pursuit of solutions to specific problems (Fischer, G., Rohde, M., & Wulf, V. (2007).

2.2 Communities of interest (CoI)

CoIs can be thought of as "communities of communities" (Brown & Duguid, 1991). CoIs are also defined by their shared interest in framing and resolution of a design problem, are more temporary than CoPs, come together in the context of a specific project and dissolve after the project has ended.

Among central concepts and models for working and learning within CoIs are the following (Fischer et al., 2007; Fischer & Shipman, 2010):

Common ground and shared understanding (Clark & Brennan, 1991): As CoI are more temporal than CoPs and come together in the context of a specific project and dissolve after the project has ended, creating common ground and shared understanding is the major challenge for CoIs

Symmetry of ignorance: refers to “the inevitably incomplete competence of an individual” (Fischer, 2000; Rittel, 1984). Therefore, “even within disciplines, disciplinary competence is not achieved in individual minds, but as a collective achievement made possible by the overlap of narrow specialties” (Campbell, 1969). This is especially relevant for XR4HUMAN due to competence diversity of its stakeholder population.

Social creativity: A strength of CoIs is their potential for creativity. One of the sources of this creativity is “symmetry of ignorance” because different backgrounds and different perspectives can lead to new insights. Therefore, CoIs have great potential to be more innovative and more transforming than a single CoP (Fischer, 2001; Fischer et al., 2005, Fischer et al., 2007).

The “symmetry of ignorance” is particularly interesting, since it underscores the importance of diversity in needs and competences that may be mutually developed within a CoI. A CoI thus has more potential to become more innovative and transformative. At the same time, stakeholders within a CoI may be seen as “informed participants”, in that they are neither experts nor novices, but both (Fisher et al 2007), as is the case in XR4HUMAN. The role of certain individuals is paramount for development in networks and communities. These are “key species” (Nardi and O’Day, 1999). They are people with special skills, personal and social abilities and interests that are essential to the well-functioning of an information ecology.

Gladwell identifies “three agents of change” (Gladwell 2002). **(1) There is the law of the few.** Change comes about only when the significant 20 % of a population is involved and dedicated to the forces of change. To Gladwell there are three types of key species:

- The *connector*: an individual with special social gifts and abilities. The connector is an expert in making friends and keeping contacts active. The connector may also act as boundary spanners by moving information and context from one group of people to another (Cross and Parker 2004). An example in XR4HUMAN context is a networking association such as XR4EUROPE or other national clusters such as VRBB, FIVR, INMERSIVA XR etc.
- The *maven*: an “information specialist”, a person who thrives on spreading his knowledge. The maven is also characterized by his social skills and his ability to get across the message so that others believe what they say. An XR4HUMAN-relevant example are academic stakeholders that are knowledgeable in the field of XR and active in dissemination and popularization activities.
- The *salesman*: one that possesses qualities of persuasion and negotiation and makes him/her important in order to point those in the network in the right direction and provides the common ground. In XR4HUMAN context, these could be policy-making public bodies.

Identifying and nourishing the different key species in the network/Col, then, becomes an important aspect in network maintenance and network development, and will be incorporated in the XR4Human community methodology.

(2). Gladwell talks of the **stickiness factor**, which refers to the nature of the content, or the immediate response the content receives in the environment it is introduced. Social media, such as Facebook, has this stickiness factor that makes it irresistible. Identification of the appropriate social media strategies will be the focus of XR4HUMAN's Work Package 8.

(3). The **power of context**. This relates to the way pressure and norms among peers may contribute to the development and spread of new ideas and practices. This process will be defined by the changing and emergent XR landscape in Europe.

In Gladwell's perspective the quality of the change depends on the quality of the characteristics in the network. Trust is a keyword here, as are personal qualifications and abilities. Some of these are inherent and cannot easily be taught or passed on through participation in a community. Nardi et al. also observes the need to develop higher level skills when working in a network setting. Dealing with people from different organizations, with different social and cultural backgrounds, necessitates an understanding for genre sensitivity, as well as context and cultural sensitivity. As an example, Nardi et al. stress the need to be sensitive to language codes in different settings, and the necessity to adapt to the situation (Nardi, Whitaker and Schwarz, 2002). Therefore, in XR4HUMAN context, it is important to make cultural and social sensitivity and inclusion an integral part of stakeholder engagement methodology.

2.3 Framework for characterizing communities: domain, network, practice

We characterize XR4HUMAN communities in line with the framework suggested by (Wenger et al, 2002), along the dimensions of domain, community/network and practice.

The central components of the **domain** are:

- The goals, central issues, topics of interests;
- Strategic intents: helping, best-practice, knowledge-stewardship, innovation;
- Organizations and strategies;
- Community's outputs: project outcomes, gaming elements, additions to the repository etc.

The **community/network** is characterized by (Wenger et al., 2002):

- The involved “stakeholders” and members, their roles, skills, resources, motivations;
- Existing social networks as a basis for community and “social fabric” of learning (Wenger et al., 2002);
- Rules for membership and members’ movement along the participation trajectory;
- Cross-cultural aspects: what is the actual corporate culture/cultures in terms of dimensions as described by Hofstede (Hofstede 1984) and Lewis (Lewis 2005);
- Distributed vs. local nature: what are the interactions and encounters supported? Is there support for “chance meetings between individuals with similar interests and motivation” (Pemberton, Malvin & Stalker, 2007)?
- Organizational context: is the community offshoot of any formal or informal groupings in the organization?

Practice is identified by the following characteristics:

- How are activities and processes organized?
- How/what kind of knowledge is managed?
- Organization of knowledge repository;
- Community’s needs in terms of technological support, guidance, mentors, facilitators, etc.;
- To what extent the organizational structure provides support for the community.

The XR4HUMAN communities will typically consist of several highly diverse and multi-disciplinary components and constellations, including XR professionals and developers, policy makers, researchers, and general public (users and non-users of XR technologies). The community methodology will thus have to take into consideration how the specific XR4HUMAN community is composed and what its cultural and organizational characteristics are. We assume that XR4HUMAN stakeholders would like to address domains that are of an emergent nature that typically would have ill-defined problems and a high level of complexity, developing new practices that may be turned into new business opportunities. Such domains are typically multidisciplinary, and span across several research and business areas.

With regard to XR4HUMAN, the domain will be defined by the common or shared interests that provide the passion or incentive, such as ethical and inclusive XR. At the same time, for XR4HUMAN communities/networks, what may be interesting are not only new domains, but also new types of competences and new focus areas within the domain. Also, reflecting upon the current trends in project management and innovation, it might be e.g. what is “hot”, relevant and sought after in a domain. Learning communities are typically self-organizing and self-sustained entities within an organization or

across organizations. Consequently, they are in many ways difficult to herd, or give directions or assignments. Joint practices relevant for XR4HUMAN goals will need to be established and to facilitate the development of communities through different phases of their lifecycle. As all living organisms, communities are not static and typically transit through different phases during their lifecycle. The different major stages in a community life can be shortly outlined as follows (Wenger et al, 2002):

- Early/seeding: planning, launching, coalescing;
- Mature/sustaining: maturing, consolidating, stewarding;
- Final phase: transformation.

2.4 Seven Principles for Cultivating a Community

In the above, we have outlined a rather complex picture of networks and CoIs, and how they may be understood. In the following, we will suggest some ways of cultivating CoIs within the context of the XR4HUMAN project, meaning design principles applied to keep the community alive through the different phases of their lifecycle. Based on Wenger, McDermott and Snyder (Wenger, McDermott and Snyder 2002), seven design principles for cultivating communities and networks are presented:

- **Principle 1. Design for evolution:** Communities are developed from personal networks, and the evolutionary nature of the community should be reflected in how the social and organizational structures are devised.
- **Principle 2. Open a dialogue between inside and outside perspectives:** the design of a community should include some outside perspective, in order to have both a critical and creative view on the perspectives of the community.
- **Principle 3. Invite different levels of participation:** community members frequently move between different levels of participation (core, active and peripheral groups), depending on the focus and development of the domain or activities at any given point. This movement should be seen as healthy and welcome and communities should “build benches” to secure future increased involvement.
- **Principle 4. Develop both public and private community spaces:** communities need both open (one-to-many/many-to-many) and more closed (one-to-one) channels of communication and interaction. Informal channels are equally important as formal channels, if not more important.
- **Principle 5. Focus on value:** communities are basically voluntary, and the value of participation is not always immediately evident, therefore, it should be qualified and

communicated clearly. The aspect of value in communities is of an emergent nature; it is a composition of entities (participants, artifacts, networks) inherent in the community that are not immediately apparent.

- **Principle 6. Combine familiarity and excitement:** On the one hand, the community should provide a haven, a getaway place for its members where they can receive, and give, comfort and belonging from like-minded people. On the other hand, the community should provide opportunities and affordances not readily found in their primary organization.
- **Principle 7. Create a rhythm for the community:** rhythm is created by regularity, frequency and pace of events. Identifying the activities may assist to monitor the rhythm, the relations developed, the interactions among the participants and the topics they engage in.
- Designing for the purpose of cultivating communities implies that a focus should be on facilitating on possible activities, ensuring energy and pace rather than structure. Design of the environment should be an iterative process and not a precursor to the establishment of the community.

In the following, we provide recommendations for stimulating and supporting XR4HUMAN communities during the different phases of their development, combining the presented theoretical background with the stakeholder engagement literature.

3 Towards XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement methodology

3.1 Identifying Principles for Cultivating a Community of XR4HUMAN Stakeholders

3.1.1 Choosing the engagement approach

XR4HUMAN is a project with goals that require a variety of stakeholder groups, partners and communities: from software developers to bloggers, government officials and researchers, consumers of XR technologies, as well as people who know nothing about XR technology. Therefore, in developing a stakeholder engagement plan and working with such diverse stakeholders, it is important to take each specific case into account and keep in mind the common unifying goal of creating ethical, inclusive, democratic, and sustainable standards for the use of XR technologies. To do this we draw on the framework proposed by (Wenger 2002) for supporting communities of interest along the dimensions of domain, network and practice:

Defining **domain** is the first step in selecting a methodology for engaging different stakeholders, as it focuses on the goals and value of the XR4HUMAN project for each stakeholder group. With correctly formulated goals and clearly defined value, the engagement of key stakeholders will develop into a partnership, because if each project participant is aware of their own purpose and the importance of interaction, the project will gain not only participants, but also valuable collaborators.

Network dimension in XR4HUMAN context considers the establishment and alignment of communication channels, workshops, presentations, and specially organized events are activities that are paramount in stakeholder outreach. It is advisable to create formal and informal channels of communication, meetings, and feedback, to take into account different levels of engagement, exposure and heterogeneity of stakeholders, and to overcome "symmetry of ignorance". This will help create a more trusting and lasting relationship, support cooperation, and resolve possible misunderstandings.

Establishing **joint practice** is a necessary step of work with stakeholders and focuses on the organization of events and activities that are important for the successful functioning of the project, interaction with stakeholders and in general healthy development of communities of interest. It is also important to consider the technological aspects of stakeholder communication and the technological side of event management and communication channels' technical support.

3.1.2 From ignorance to creativity

A recurring feature of many stakeholder engagement approaches is the lack of due attention to the problem of "symmetry of ignorance" (Todeschini, B. V., 2020). Instead of being a constraining element, the "symmetry of ignorance" can provide the basis for stakeholder creativity. Connecting different viewpoints and attempting to create a common awareness between all stakeholders can produce new understandings, ideas, and artifacts. Community creativity in the XR4HUMAN context can be encouraged by new ways of communication and interaction that allow the owners of the project to contribute to the expression and solution of the problems. These new ways of interaction must be designed from a stakeholder-oriented perspective, creating an environment in which stakeholders can change roles and act as designers, developers, scientists, and customers. An example of this approach are the demonstration events planned in WP6 where members of both the public and policy makers will be able to visit demonstrator labs provided by XR4HUMAN consortium and contribute with their feedback and insights, contributing to the deliverables and results of the project. Breaches in communication often occur when stakeholders come from different backgrounds (Snow, 1993) and use different standards, symbols, and representations. Different points of view help to discover alternatives and uncover implicit aspects of situations.

To introduce important perspectives into the process of designing, working, and carrying on the life of a project, different groups of stakeholders should be designers and co-developers, not just consumers and observers (Fischer, 1998). End users, businesses, and researchers, as owners of final problems, bring perspectives to collaborative project efforts that are especially important for articulating and mitigating potential problems. The "symmetry of ignorance" requires the creation of spaces and places that serve as boundary objects where different cultures and stakeholder groups can meet and interact. Boundary objects of misunderstanding serve as points of contact that capture different areas of human knowledge, the accumulation and dissemination of which can lead to an increase in socially shared cognition and practice (Resnik et al., 1991). Examples are XR4HUMAN forums, repositories, and events. Recognising that most ethics-related and technology acceptance problems are characterized by a "symmetry of ignorance" leads to a different view of learning. In situations in which mutual understanding does not exist, it cannot simply be passed on by the community groups that have it to the people who need it. Therefore, approaches required that view engagement and working on ethical norms as a collaborative knowledge construction (Scardamalia, 1994).

Hence, by encouraging the process of stakeholder interaction within a shared context defined by the task at hand, opportunities can emerge from enhancing the creation of shared understanding. This process - that shall be pursued during the XR4HUMAN project - melds the mutual understanding that is collaboratively constructed into the problem-solving context, enhancing the process as well as the stakeholders and allowing them to participate from a more enriched and meaningful perspective (Brown, 1994). This includes creating activities and defining lines of work relevant to the task at hand and supporting the interaction of multiple perspectives and diverse stakeholders that allow each stakeholder to jointly explore knowledge and a shared understanding of the main tasks. XR4HUMAN workshops, presentations, and communication forums serve the co-design process by providing the "right" information at the "right" time and in the "right" way.

3.2 XR4HUMAN Stakeholder Engagement methodology

Consequently, taking into account relevant theoretical frameworks and literature, previous experiences and carefully considering the key models of stakeholder engagement and work, and taking into account the ethics, inclusivity and sustainability-related focus of XR4HUMAN, the following model of engagement has been proposed. The stakeholders in the project are very different social and industrial groups: Industry and Developers associations, Consumer Associations, Civil society organizations, General public, Research Policy makers, Legal experts, content developers, Members of Research Ethics Councils, Science journalists and general public users.

For a comprehensive connection and working plan of engagement, as well as to implement the activities taking place and to establish channels of communication and dissemination, building on Deliverable 8.1 and consortium partners' collective intelligence identifying stakeholders and engagement activities, a 7-step plan is proposed. This model is based on the stakeholder engagement approaches discussed in the theoretical part - the literary review and the principles of community building. The eclectic method of generating the model provides an adaptation of the model to the XR4HUMAN project, by selecting engagement steps based on the specific stakeholders of the project. The following is a detailed step-by-step breakdown of the proposed model for the identification of relevant stakeholders.

First step: Monitor - is essential for the stakeholder identification and common to almost all engagement models discussed in the theoretical part and is important for identifying and selecting the significant and most vulnerable stakeholder groups. This step must be implemented during the preparatory phase of the project, which also forms an integral part of the stakeholder engagement plan.

Second step: Message is an essential and very important step in working with project stakeholders, it allows to establish a channel of communication and to provide stakeholders with information, to involve them in project activities. This step is found in all stakeholder engagement models and the 7 community principles under different names: Dialogue, Communication, and Negotiation.

Third step: Value creation. A focus on creating value for each stakeholder group builds a strong link between the project and the stakeholders. It helps to overcome the symmetry of ignorance, where each stakeholder group brings its own values and important issues, provides the possibility to share and discuss it, and at the end, promotes social creativity. This step is present in the UNEP model and the 7 community principles.

Fourth step: Involve is an important practical step of communication and comprehensive stakeholder involvement in project activities. This step is used in the 7 community principles (Participation) as well as in UNEP and The International Association for Public Participation Stakeholder Engagement models.

Fifth step: Collaborate ensures multi-level stakeholder participation in the project, which helps to overcome the symmetry of ignorance, foster mutual exchange of information between stakeholders, and provide reinforcement for the most vulnerable and most disengaged stakeholders. This step is presented in all stakeholder engagement plans except the Good Faith approach and makes use of public and private community spaces (7 principles)

Sixth step: Empower allows the democratic and inclusive, sustainable stakeholder engagement, which is the key to achieving the goals of the XR4HUMAN project. Empower technique is

relevant for The International Association for Public Participation, Good Faith stakeholder engagement models and 7 community principles.

Seventh step: Innovate is a necessity for the longevity of the project and the achievement of its goals, as technology advances and society evolves, which creates new challenges and fields of cooperation and partnership.

All these steps are aimed at improving communication, the evolution of stakeholders into trustworthy partners and the further development of joint cooperation in the future.

Table 9 illustrates the findings and key steps of the engagement approach

Table 9: Seven-step XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement plan

ENGAGEMENT APPROACH	MAIN GOALS	OVERVIEW	IMPLEMENTATION
MONITOR	Identifying and tracking Stakeholder groups	Determination of the stakeholders' position, the key concerns, the level of exposure to the project, and the involvement status.	Project groundwork phase (proposal drafting), preparation of D8.1, and consultations with the EC at the early phase of the project)
MESSAGE	Establishing communication with stakeholders	Networking with different stakeholder groups, considering the specifics, requirements, and preferences of communication pathways	Website Social media e-newsletters

<p>CREATE VALUE</p>	<p>Uniting stakeholders under a central goal of the XR4HUMAN project, considering the special needs of each group</p>	<p>XR4HUMAN involves various stakeholder groups. Each stakeholder group has its own needs, interests, and spheres of influence in the project. To successfully engage each group, it is essential to create value for each stakeholder and unite them beneath the ethical, sustainable umbrella of the overarching goal.</p>	<p>Scientific publications, Workshops, Conferences, Forum Lab visits</p>
<p>INVOLVE</p>	<p>Ensuring the involvement and participation of stakeholders at different levels</p>	<p>The development of the project is a constant motion, a shift in emphasis and the movement of participants in the process. This allows stakeholders to better understand each other, overcome miscommunications, create new sustainable connections, and establish partnerships</p>	<p>Workshops, Social media, Public events, Lab visits Forum</p>

<p>COLLABORATE</p>	<p>Excitement - Acknowledgement - Familiarity</p>	<p>To fulfill the goals of the project, it is important to ensure the adoption of XR technologies and primarily to arouse the general public' interest and excitement, to familiarize key stakeholders with the use of technologies, and to establish the technologies as a familiar practice. This also works for the involvement of developers and scientists, as the adaptation of ethical standards in products follows the same adoption pattern.</p>	<p>Workshops, Social media, Conferences, Public events, Forum</p>
<p>EMPOWER</p>	<p>The final decision-making is in the hands of the key stakeholders.</p>	<p>All stakeholders, including the most vulnerable and affected by the project, must be provided assurances of ethical safety and inclusiveness at the outcome of the project.</p>	<p>Website, Social media, Conferences, Press release, Forum Lab visits</p>

<p>INNOVATE</p>	<p>Shared work on common objectives of the project and its Stakeholders. Include co-creation and co-implementation of new ideas</p>	<p>To create and maintain long-term stakeholder engagement and participation, it is important to create new goals together and develop cooperation and partnerships</p>	<p>Workshops, Social media, Scientific conferences, Website, Forum Lab visits</p>
-----------------	---	---	---

Hence, following the proposed plan will ensure comprehensive and multifaceted stakeholder participation in project execution, as well as long-term stakeholder engagement and trusted partnerships. It offers mutually beneficial collaboration and diverse partnerships that help overcome misunderstandings among stakeholders, create the value of communication and collaboration, and bring different groups together under one goal while keeping in mind the specific needs of each stakeholder, which is the guarantee of the successful implementation of the entire project.

3.3 XR4Human Stakeholder Engagement methodology

3.3.1 Building a strong XR4HUMAN Stakeholder database and analysis

As highlighted in the theoretical approach of the stakeholder engagement methodology (including the new 7 steps Monitor, Message, Create Value, Involve, Collaborate, Empower, Innovate and principles for nurturing communities of interest), XR4HUMAN project will require the strategic development of a stakeholder database to ensure a differentiated engagement action plan for each, depending on their specific requirements, interests, influence, but also fostering an inclusive outreach to most vulnerable and least informed stakeholder groups (non-users of the technology, individuals with disabilities etc), which fully correspond to the first monitor step of the Stakeholder engagement plan.

We will build the XR4HUMAN database by collecting stakeholders information via a GDPR-compliant form (Monitor step). This form will be the ubiquitous entry point to register, to ensure that all stakeholders are informed, get access to and participate in XR4HUMAN activities and the co-design of various outputs such as the Code of Conduct, the Interoperability Guidelines and the Rating System (Message, Involve and Collaborate steps).

To grow the database, two main distribution channels will be put in place. The consortium members will invite their respective networks to fill in a form (Appendix). Registration will also be accessible via a dedicated section on the website. From the onset, the form shall be designed in a way that enables to have identical information horizontally - across various channels of activities and communication; for instance, newsletter, forum and the outreach for working groups' sessions. The rationale behind having the same form that serves as the basis of all data collected throughout the XR4HUMAN project will help the XR4HUMAN consortium swiftly identify and assess KPIs (e.g., the number of participants under a specific stakeholder profile etc.) according to a single database used across all Work Packages (WPs) (Collaborate and Involve steps).

In line with the theoretical underpinnings in section 2.4, this form and in turn, the data collected, shall enable to gain an overview of the stakeholder profiles (Table 9), while allowing to determine via questions stakeholders' area(s) and level of knowledge, expertise, interest, proactivity (i.e. commitment to contribute to XR4HUMAN's outputs), and the type of commitment they are inclined to undertake (e.g. being informed, being consulted on a regular or irregular basis, etc.) (Create Value, Collaborate and Empower steps). To do so, questions will be included in the form to gauge and weigh the engagement level of stakeholders, with a possible rating from 1 to 10 or binary answers, and may include:

- Are you interested in ethics?
- Are you engaged in an ethics organization?
- Have you ever participated in an ethics working group?
- Would you be interested in participating in an ethics working group?

This knowledge will in turn facilitate which stakeholder should be engaged or not for a specific activity connected to the WPs deliverables. As regards communication for incentivizing participation in stakeholder engagement activities, the database will be used by the WP8 Communication and Dissemination partners, with the set-up of a XR4HUMAN-specific email address that will funnel invitations with content specific to the engagement event and/or to the specific type of stakeholder. The content of the invitations will be drafted by the relevant WP leaders that will organize the engagement events. The gatekeepers of this database will be WP1 leaders (Message, Involve, Collaborate steps).

3.3.2 XR4HUMAN Encounters and stakeholder engagement activities

The Consortium will be involving the stakeholders in various activities throughout the duration of the XR4HUMAN project so that their input can feed into the consortium's co-creation of the Code of Conduct, Interoperability Guidelines and Rating system. These engagements will be facilitated with the 7-step stakeholder engagement plan developed for the XR4HUMAN project. Implementing the steps of

Creation Value, Involve, Collaborate and Empower with the key stakeholders will be beneficial for the main objectives of the project.

Personas for stakeholder engagement may be categorized within four broad categories and will be involved in specific engagement activities. Table 10 shows broad similarities with Table 2 from D8.1. Yet, it should be highlighted that the categories of such stakeholder personas for engagement purposes will become more granular and refined over the course of the project, thanks to the consortium’s collective intelligence and networks, as well as the launch of the database.

Table 10: Personas

Personas	Description
Policy makers	Need to be informed to keep abreast with how these XR technologies, applications and environments impact our society and possible harms and risks related to them, with a view to regulating this sector so as to protect citizens from harmful deviations and ensure that European XR market players have a level playing field to compete, grow, and create jobs.
Non-profit organizations (association, foundation, social organizations etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They would have a community impacted by the XR4HUMAN work and would need to inform them - They would already be working on the topic and would like to share their findings - They may include organizations that have a team dedicated to digitalization, ones that are highly prone to the digital transformation brought by the XR technology uptake in the near future (e.g. training, education, medical, and other fields), or ones that have a membership base or audiences who are prone to or currently marginalized.
Companies (all types of businesses, users or non-users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They would be impacted by the work of XR4HUMAN - They would like to know how to make business out of this new stream of information - They would need to adapt their work by XR4HUMAN’s Code of Conduct and other guidelines
General Public (users and non-users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They would be the final users of these technologies: from work to their personal digital life, they will share increasing amounts of information and data, requiring them to know about data collection and management.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Families and parents are concerned for the next generation and their children’s exposure to potential harms and risks.
--	--

Each persona will participate to varying extents in the following activities to foster a comprehensive knowledge base of XR4HUMAN. Those personas’ outlooks and insights are paramount for the consortium members to gain an overview of the needs or concerns, and in turn, to generate constructive cross-disciplinary and for facilitating cross-sectoral discussions from all parties. These personas with their different perspectives will constitute the ‘symmetry of ignorance’ of the XR4HUMAN community, that allow to create new ways of collaboration and partnership in the creation of ethical, inclusive and sustainable norms of using the XR technologies. In addition, such collaboration contributes to ‘social creativity’ and development of shared understanding of XR4HUMAN ethical framework through the steps of Create Value, Collaborate and Innovate.

The stakeholder engagement activities that shall take place as part of WP1 T1.4 XR4Human Encounters and T1.2 Management of the XR4Human European Forum encompass the following tasks of the project **(See table 11 below and appendix 9 for the Gantt Chart)**.

Tables 11: Stakeholder engagement timeline

WP	Task	Type of Stakeholder Engagement Action	Stakeholder personas	Lead	Support	Month (M)
WP3	T3.1 Policy debate analysis (M1-M6)	Consultation: Mostly through the Forum Step 2 of Stakeholder engagement plan - Message (Table 7)	Policy makers	KIT	XR4EU	M1-M6
	T3.4 Governance debate forum (M13-M36)	Consultation: Mostly through the Forum and workshop(s) can be envisaged to corroborate findings. Other	Policy maker, non profit organization	KIT	XR4EU	M13-M36

		forms (cf. Table 7) may be deployed Step 3 - Create Value (Table 7)				
WP4	T4.2 Co-create Interoperability Guideline (M10-M24)	Consultation: Mostly through the Forum and workshop(s) can be envisaged to corroborate findings. Other forms (cf. Table 7) may be deployed Step 4 - Create Value (Table 7)	All personas	USN	XR4EU	M10-M24
WP5	T5.2 Stakeholder consultations	Consultation: Forum and workshops Step 5 - Involve (Table 7)	All personas	USN	XR4EU	M16-M24
	Task 5.3 Creation of the XR Code of Conduct	Consultation: Mostly through the Forum and workshop(s) can be envisaged to corroborate findings. Other forms (Table 7) may be deployed Step 6 - Collaborate (Table 7)	All personas	USN	XR4EU	M22-36
WP6	T6.1 Definition, Identification and selection of case studies	Step 6 - Empower (Table 7)	Non profit organization	HHI	XR4EU	M1-M12

	T6.4 Evaluation of example use cases	Recruitment of participants to test the use cases and evaluate Step 6 - Collaborate (Table 7)	All personas	HHI	XR4EU	M20-M36
WP7	Task 7.2 Elicitation of needs, requirements and experiences from stakeholders	Consultation: Workshop(s), survey, and Forum discussions Step 7 - Innovate (Table 7)	All personas	IFE	XR4EU	M7-M18

3.3.2.1 The Website

The website will be central in the Message step of Stakeholder engagement methodology. As mentioned above, the stakeholders will find information on the XR4HUMAN project and have a form to fill to get information from the consortium activities and register to the forum (Message and Involve steps).

3.3.2.2 The Forum

The Forum will be the meeting point between the consortium and the stakeholders and serve as a 'boundary object', used to develop "shared ground and understanding" (see Chapter 3), that will ensure involvement and collaboration among stakeholders within the project . On the one hand, it will allow the consortium to share their findings, new information, working groups' outputs and provisional work. On the other hand, stakeholders will have the opportunity to engage in the comment sections to share expertise and contributions on any missing topics or points, enabling the development of WPs requirements and deliverables as specified in the Grant Agreement (Create Value, Involve, Collaborate steps).

The goal is to bring together cross-European and cross-sectoral perspectives, to enhance adherence to recommendations such as the Code of Conduct and its validation, the Interoperability Guidelines, and the Rating System. By taking a starting point from the existing 'symmetry of ignorance', stemming from the different competencies and features of the participants, the Forum will facilitate

social creativity in the XR4HUMAN community to meet the project goals and correspond to steps: Empower, Collaborate, Create Value and Innovate.

Image: A provisional mockup of the Forum

For legacy (i.e. technical sustainability) purposes, the Forum will be hosted on XR4EUROPE's website in addition to its animation there as well, allowing to circumvent migration cost of the forum from XR4Human's website to XR4EUROPE's at the end of XR4Human's project. A redirection link to the forum will also be foreseen on the XR4HUMAN Website.

3.3.2.3 Working Groups

Following the need of information from each personas, a group of stakeholders will be appointed to study and report on a particular question and make recommendations based on its findings, as a part of Involve and Empower steps.

Coordinated by XR4EUROPE, each consortium member will be able to create working groups (WGs) to facilitate the development of the Code of conduct, Interoperability Guidelines and Rating System. To do so, a guideline document for the good set-up and functioning of working groups and associated outputs, will be given to consortium members or working groups' partners. This will ensure working groups' homogeneous quality throughout the project, and support consortium members or partners' autonomy on organizing such working groups. By doing so, we will harmonize the minimum information required by each working groups' outputs. Moreover, the formation of WG helps to innovate "symmetry of ignorance" into creative partnership and empower stakeholders.

Here is a list of possible topics based on the work of the consortium:

- state-of-the art in ethical frameworks, code of conduct and good practices
- overview of risks and harms arising from XR risks
- model of harm that could arise from the use of XR technologies
- ethical issues beyond risks and harm
- Interoperability, ethical framework, and user rating policy roadmap

The working groups will be held throughout the XR4HUMAN duration and will be dependent on the consortium's progress on specific work. Those WGs will be essential in supporting the close feedback loop between stakeholders and the consortium partners developing their work (Create value step). Working groups will be done upon request and contingent on consortium members' needs.

3.3.2.4 Participating in conferences and events

To allow the XR4HUMAN project to expand and meet current and new stakeholders, it will be necessary to participate in events from various fields and industries (Message, Involve, Collaborate and Empower steps):

- As a speaker on a conference track on topics such as ethics and interoperability
- As a speaker for a paper written by the consortium
- As a speaker in a poster session

- As exhibitors on an event where stakeholders could register for the forum
- As a working group organizer during an event
- As an attendee to network and meet new stakeholders

Taking part in such events will help XR4HUMAN to be known and be part of the community. This will allow the XR4HUMAN consortium to gain real value in the eyes of the stakeholders.

Below is a non-exhaustive list of relevant events that have been identified by the consortium. This list is indicative of the possible events the consortium members could attend. These events are European or worldwide events but with a critical mass of European visitors. The targeted audience are B2B, Researcher, B2C, and the general public.

Date & Location	Event	Website	Topic
23-24 Jan 2023 Paris (FR)	ICVARS Paris - International Conference on Virtual and Augmented Reality	https://waset.org/virtual-and-augmented-reality-conference-in-january-2023-in-paris	Augmented Reality
31 Jan-3 Feb 2023 Barcelona (ES)	ISE - Integrated Systems Europe	https://www.iseurope.org/	AV and systems integration exhibition event
27 Feb-2 March 2023 Barcelona (ES)	MWC - Mobile World Congress	https://www.virtuality.fr/en	Theme "Velocity": 5G, 6G, immersive technology and fintech
16-17 March 2023 Paris (FR)	Virtuality	https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/	Business Event dedicated to Web3 Industries: Blockchain XR, Metaverse
29-31 March 2023 Angoulême (FR)	Immersity	https://www.immersity.fr/	New forms of Storytelling in XR
5-9 Apr 2023 Paris (FR)	New Images	https://newimages-hub.com/	Digital creation and virtual worlds Festival

12-16 Apr 2023 Laval (FR)	Laval Virtual	https://laval-virtual.com/en/	Global XR
3 June 2023 Hamburg (DE)	VRHAM! Virtual Reality & Arts Festival	https://www.vrham.de/	VR and art
7-10 June 2023 Tokyo (JA)	JSSTS Society for Philosophy and Technology Japan	https://www.spt2023.org/	Technology and Mobility
15-16 June 2023 Stuttgart (DE)	XR Expo	https://www.vdc-fellbach.de/en/xr-expo/	B2B tech event: XR applications in industry, architecture, health, trade and handicraft
TBD	Philosophy of Human Technology Relations Conference	https://www.aau.dk/	Human-Tech interaction
TBD (Autumn) Paris (FR)	MetaDays	https://metadays.fr/	B2B Event: Content and Business
27 Nov - 1 Dec 2023 Rotterdam (NL)	Immersive Tech Week	https://vrdays.co/	Global XR
29 Nov 2023 Helsinki (FI)	Match XR	https://www.matchxrhelsinki.com/	A pre-Slush event: XR, Web3, gaming
18 - 20 Oct 2023 Brussels (BE)	Stereopsia	https://stereopsia.com/	Global XR
24-25 Oct 2023 Vienna (AT)	AWE EU	https://www.awexr.com/eu-2023/	Global XR

7-8 Sept 2023 Paris (FR)	ENRIO Congress on Research Integrity practice	http://www.enrio.eu/ congress2023/	Research Integrity
16-20 Oct 2023 Sydney (ASTL)	ISMAR 2023: IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality	https://www.ismar.net/ t/	Academic conference in the fields of Augmented Reality and Mixed Reality
2-5 June 2024 Athens (GR)	World Conference on Research Integrity	https://wcrif.org/	Research Integrity

3.3.2.5 Organisation of final conference

At the end of the 3 years will be held the eXtended into the future conference by the XR4HUMAN consortium to inform the stakeholder of the final results of the code of conduct, interoperability guidance and rating system.

This Conference will be a presentation of the work through 3 years, the various working groups and studies, the outcomes and the path to it, the discussions and interactions with the stakeholders leading to the final documents.

All stakeholders, including each network of the consortium and the European Commission, will be invited to discover the findings and results of the XR4HUMAN project (Create Value and Innovate steps).

3.3.2.6 Legacy

At the end of the XR4HUMAN project, the XR4EUROPE website will keep the Forum open and running on their website, have regular working groups on the ethics and evolution of tech feeding the European bodies and Institutions with updates on the need from the market and beyond (Innovate step).

4 Conclusion: towards XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement methodology

The topic of stakeholder engagement is gaining relevance in business, social, political, management, and philosophical research. Most empirical studies on stakeholder engagement use qualitative methods (Stutz, 2018). This can be attributed to the fact that stakeholder engagement presents a relatively new area of research compared with others. In stakeholder theory more broadly, studies that apply quantitative methods focus mostly on testing the premise of instrumental stakeholder theory that stakeholder orientation has a positive influence on an organization's financial performance (Ayuso, 2014). However, the literature lacks validated measurement models of stakeholder engagement so that scholars can test its relationship with financial performance (Laude, 2020).

As indicated in the discussion chapter, for the successful execution of the XR4HUMAN project, we conclude that it was necessary to develop an eclectic, inclusive and comprehensive approach to stakeholder engagement to reach the main goals and policy of the project. During the development of the new model, it was vital to choose relevant parts of existing models and adapt them to a new XR4Human model, supplementing it with elements from community of interest literature (such as seven principles of communities and symmetry of ignorance). The new XR4HUMAN 7-step stakeholder engagement model considers the diversity and specificity in its approach to identify stakeholders ensuring a human-centered, inclusive, sustainable, and democratic way for society to adapt and embrace XR technology. The developed model is reinforced by activities, events and tools that ensure stakeholder participation and collaboration throughout the life of the project and provide the foundation for the future ethical development of the use of XR technologies. The next step is integrally related to it, is selecting the right stakeholder engagement plan to maximize the success of the project's objectives.

4.1 Summary: XR4HUMAN Stakeholder Engagement Methodology

Stakeholder engagement is a multi-layered, diverse, and exciting creative process. The successful performance of the engagement process requires consideration of the nuances and specifics of the project, the diversity of stakeholders, the varying levels of influence and involvement of interest groups. A comprehensive literature review of current stakeholder engagement models was conducted to choose the best option for a new methodology implementation. Five modern multidisciplinary methodologies were reviewed in detail, each of them introducing important steps to create the best model for the XR4HUMAN project. The theoretical part also includes a detailed analysis of related work on the topic of communities of interest, including seven principles for cultivating communities' model.

Based on the theory, an eclectic stakeholder engagement methodology was developed including seven steps of XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement. The issue of "symmetry of ignorance" evolved into a creative partnership, ensuring collaborative and inclusive engagement. The methodology is supported by a 3-year plan of activities with stakeholders complying with the framework of the XR4HUMAN project. This plan constitutes the implementation of XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement and consists of practical events, tools and activities with stakeholders. The engagement methodology as well as the recommended activities are designed for comprehensive, inclusive stakeholder engagement, to foster ethical, inclusive and sustainable development and use of XR technologies in Europe.

4.2 Risk factors and limitations: Monitoring stakeholder communities from a SWOT perspective.

The XR4HUMAN stakeholder methodology addresses the need for the development of a robust and sustainable model for implementation on the one hand, and on the other, acknowledges the complexity and unpredictability in the ways in which networks and communities are nourished and developed. Therefore, we propose continuous monitoring of activities based on what we perceive to be critical factors in the development.

A SWOT analysis may be an adequate tool for monitoring and giving basis for contingency plans and interventions. The SWOT analysis also needs to be regularly updated to incorporate the dynamics and development of the project. A SWOT analysis is particularly important in the initial phases of any project. We hope that our comprehensive literature review has made the participants of XR4HUMAN more aware of the complexities and nuances of what a stakeholder is, how to approach and engage stakeholders, and what methodologies may work to that end. This also means that the composition of stakeholders are important; who are they, how can they contribute to each other's needs and development.

A SWOT analysis is presented in Table 14, including but not limited to (to be filled in continuously):

SWOT Analysis: XR4HUMAN

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What strengths do XR4Human possess? • What needs to be added? • What strengths do we see in our methodology? • How can the strengths be enhanced/improved? <p><i>Examples of possible strengths:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The ability to decision-making, to have a clear vision and strategy. ❖ Being context sensitive ❖ “Listening to the ground”: the ability to stay in touch with what is going on. ❖ High level of competence among stakeholders ❖ Ability to develop competence. ❖ Agile management style ❖ Targeted communication internally and externally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What weaknesses do XR4 Humans possess? • How can these weaknesses be minimized? <p><i>Examples of possible weaknesses:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Time available - competing engagements the strain on stakeholders ❖ The breadth of the stakeholder group becomes too wide, difficult to create and maintain unifying initiatives. ❖ Establishing mindshare among stakeholders; how to become distinguishable from the crowd.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What opportunities can XR 4 Humans provide for stakeholders/end users? • How can these opportunities be optimized, and made more visible and accessible to end users? <p><i>Examples of possible opportunities:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Sensitive to emerging possibilities not initially visible ❖ Developing technology acceptance- Code of Conduct 	<p>What are the threats to engaging stakeholders?</p> <p><i>Examples of possible threats:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Time available ❖ Competing initiatives ‘out of the blue’. ❖ Shifting priorities ❖ Fading interest among stakeholders ❖ Getting lost in the crowd; how to maintain focus from competing initiatives. ❖ Lack of technology acceptance in target audience

In addition, the 7 principles for community creation may be applied as an orienting lens.

To deal with potential threats and weaknesses, adequate measures will be applied by the consortium, in accordance with the recommendations in the presented community of interest and stakeholder engagement literature. Based on previous experiences and literature review, it seems that nurturing the relations among stakeholders, especially through communication, is paramount. A SWOT analysis also serves the purpose of functioning as a basis for formative evaluation of processes, and to assist in making changes and adjustments.

It is important to understand that the presented methodology is a starting point and will be continuously adapted and modified following the development of the project and feedback from the stakeholders.

5 REFERENCES

Granovetter, Mark (1973): The Strength of Weak Ties. *American Journal of Sociology* 78(6): 1360-1380.

Granovetter, Mark (1983): The Strength of Weak Ties: A Network Theory Revisited. *Sociological Theory*, Vol 1(1983), 201-233.

Fischer, G., Rohde, M., & Wulf, V. (2007). Community-Based Learning: The Core Competency of Residential, Research Based Universities. *International Journal for Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, Vol 2 (1), March 2007, pp. 9-40.

Wenger, E. (1998): *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*, University Press Cambridge, Cambridge, UK.

Brown, J. S., & Duguid, P. (2000) *The Social Life of Information*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.

Fischer, G. (2005) "Distances and Diversity: Sources for Social Creativity." In *Proceedings of Creativity & Cognition*, ACM, London, April, pp. 128-136.

Fischer, G. (2001) "Communities of Interest: Learning through the Interaction of Multiple Knowledge Systems," 24th Annual Information Systems Research Seminar In Scandinavia (IRIS'24), Ulvik, Norway, pp. 1-14.

Fischer, G. (2005) "Distances and Diversity: Sources for Social Creativity." In *Proceedings of Creativity & Cognition*, ACM, London, April, pp. 128-136.

Fischer, G. (2009) "End-User Development and Meta-Design: Foundations for Cultures of Participation," *Journal of Organizational and End User Computing* p. (in press).

Fischer, G., & Giaccardi, E. (2006) "Meta-Design: A Framework for the Future of End User Development." In H. Lieberman, F. Paternò, & V. Wulf (Eds.), *End User Development*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, pp. 427-457.

Fischer, G., Giaccardi, E., Eden, H., Sugimoto, M., & Ye, Y. (2005) "Beyond Binary Choices: Integrating Individual and Social Creativity," *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies (IJHCS)* Special Issue on Computer Support for Creativity (E.A. Edmonds & L. Candy, Eds.), 63(4-5), pp. 482-512.

Fischer, G., Grudin, J., Lemke, A. C., McCall, R., Ostwald, J., Reeves, B. N., & Shipman, F. (1992) "Supporting Indirect, Collaborative Design with Integrated Knowledge-Based Design Environments," *Human Computer Interaction*, Special Issue on Computer Supported Cooperative Work, 7(3), pp. 281-314.

Fischer, G., Grudin, J., McCall, R., Ostwald, J., Redmiles, D., Reeves, B., & Shipman, F. (2001) "Seeding, Evolutionary Growth and Reseeding: The Incremental Development of

Collaborative Design Environments." In G. M. Olson, T. W. Malone, & J. B. Smith (Eds.), *Coordination Theory and Collaboration Technology*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahwah, NJ, pp. 447-472.

Fischer, G. (2005) "From Reflective Practitioners to Reflective Communities." In: *Proceedings of the HCI International Conference (HCII)*, Las Vegas, July 2005, (published on CD).

Fischer, G. & Shipman, F.: "Collaborative Design Rationale and Social Creativity in Cultures of Participation", *Human Technology: An Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments* (in press)

Fischer, G., Rohde, M., & Wulf, V. (2007). *Community-Based Learning: The Core Competency of Residential, Research Based Universities*. *International Journal for Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, Vol 2 (1), March 2007, pp. 9-40.

Fischer, G & Ostwald, J. (2002) "Seeding, Evolutionary Growth, and Reseeding: Enriching Participatory Design with Informed Participation", *Proceedings of the Participatory Design Conference (PDC'02)*, T. Binder, J. Gregory, I. Wagner (Eds.), Malmö University, Sweden, June 2002, CPSR, P.O. Box 717, Palo Alto, CA 94302, pp 135-143.

Rittel, H. (1984) "Second-Generation Design Methods." In N. Cross (Ed.), *Developments in Design Methodology*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, pp. 317-327.

Campbell, D. T. (1969) "Ethnocentrism of Disciplines and the Fish-Scale Model of Omniscience." In M. Sherif, & C. W. Sherif (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary Relationships in the Social Sciences*, Aldine Publishing Company, Chicago, pp. 328-348.

Clark, H. H., & Brennan, S. E. (1991) "Grounding in Communication." In L. B. Resnick, J. M. Levine, & S. D. Teasley (Eds.), *Perspectives on Socially Shared Cognition*, American Psychological Association, pp. 127-149.

Gladwell, Malcolm (2002): *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can make a Big Difference*. New York: Little, Brown and Co.

Gladwell, Malcolm (2002): *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can make a Big Difference*. New York: Little, Brown and Co.

Cross, Robert L. and Parker, Andrew (2004): *The Hidden Power of Social Networks. Understanding how work really gets done in organizations*. Boston: Harvard Business School Publishing Company.

Lewis, R. D. (2005): *When Cultures Collide: Leading Across Cultures* (3rd Edition), National Book Network, Boston.

Pemberton, J., Mavin, D. & Stalker, B. (2007): *Scratching beneath the surface of communities of (mal)practice. Communities of Practice – one size fits all?* (J. Pemberton (ed). Emerald Group Publishing Ltd, Bradford, UK, pp. 62-73.

Hofstede, G. (1984): *Culture's consequence: International differences in work-related values*, Beverly Hills, Sage.

Lewis, R. D. (2005): *When Cultures Collide: Leading Across Cultures* (3rd Edition), National Book Network, Boston.

Andersen, D. (2007). Group model building: problem structuring, policy simulation and decision support. *J Oper Res Soc*, 691-694.

Andriof, J. (2002). JCC theme issue: Stakeholder responsibility. *The Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 16-19.

Ayuso, S. R.-C. (2014). Maximizing stakeholders' interests: An empirical analysis of the stakeholder approach. *Business & Society*, 414-439.

Barney, J. B. (2018). Why resource-based theory's model of profit appropriation must incorporate a stakeholder perspective. *Strategic Management Journal*, 3305-3325.

Brown, John Seely and Duguid, Paul (1991): *Organizational Learning and communities of Practice: Towards a Unified View of Working*. Web: <http://www2.parc.com/ops/members/brown/papers/orglearning.html>

Bryson, J. (2004). What to do when stakeholders matter. *Public Manag Rev*, 21-53.

Calton, J. M. (2006). Social contracting in a pluralist process of moral sense making. A dialogic twist on the ISCT. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 329-346.

Castelló, I. E. (2016). Strategies of legitimacy through social media: The networked strategy. *Journal of Management Studies*, 402-432.

Chen, J. (2020). Customer participation, and green product innovation in SMEs: The mediating role of opportunity recognition and exploitation. *Journal of Business Research*, 151-162.

Coff, R. W. (1999). When competitive advantage doesn't lead to performance: The resource-based view and stakeholder bargaining power. *Organization Science*, 119-133.

Cochrane, (2017) <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook>

Cox, A. (1958). The duty to bargain in good faith. *Harvard Law review*, 1401-1442.

Dawkins, C. E. (2021). An agonistic notion of political CSR: Melding activism and deliberation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 5-19.

Dawnkins, C. (2013). The Principle of Good Faith: Toward Substantive Stakeholder Engagement. *Business review*, 210-228.

de Bakker, F. G. (2013). Social movements, civil society and corporations: Taking stock and looking ahead. *Organization studies*, 573-593.

Dmytriiev, S. D. (2021). The relationship between stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility: Differences, similarities, and implications for social issues in management. *Journal of Management studies*, 1441-1470.

Dobele, A. R. (2014). An examination of corporate social responsibility implementation and stakeholder engagement. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 145-159.

EU, E. U. (2014). eGovPoliNet: the policy community. *Newsletter No. 3*, 25-42.

Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. London: Pitman.

Fischer, G. (2000) "Social Creativity, Symmetry of Ignorance and Meta-Design," *Knowledge-Based Systems Journal (Special Issue on Creativity & Cognition)*, Elsevier Science B.V., Oxford, UK, 13(7-8), pp. 527-537.

Fischer, G., Rohde, M., & Wulf, V. (2007). *Community-Based Learning: The Core Competency of Residential, Research Based Universities*. *International Journal for Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, Vol 2 (1), March 2007, pp. 9-40.

Fischer, G. & Shipman, F.: "Collaborative Design Rationale and Social Creativity in Cultures of Participation", *Human Technology: An Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments* (in press)

Freudenreich, B. L.-F. (2020). A stakeholder theory perspective on business models: Value creation for sustainability. *Journal of Business ethics*, 3-18.

Gaal, J. (1987). The disclosure of financial information: Competitiveness and the current requirements of the duty to bargain in good faith. *Labor law journal*, 562-573.

Gladwell, Malcolm (2002): *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can make a Big Difference*. New York: Little, Brown and Co.

Ghodsvali, M. K. (2019). Review of transdisciplinary approaches to food-water-energy nexus: A guide towards sustainable. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 266-278.

Granovetter, Mark (1973): *The Strength of Weak Ties*. *American Journal of Sociology* 78(6): 1360-1380.

Granovetter, Mark (1983): *The Strength of Weak Ties: A Network Theory Revisited*. *Sociological Theory*, Vol 1(1983), 201-233.

Greenwood, M. (2007). *Stakeholder engagement: Beyond the myth of corporate responsibility*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 315-327.

Harclerode, M. A. (2016). Evaluation of the role of risk perception in stakeholder engagement to prevent lead exposure in an urban setting. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 132-142.

Harrison, J. S. (2013). *Stakeholder theory, value, and firm performance*. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 97-124.

Henri Jalo, H. P. (2021). *Extended reality technologies in small and medium-sized European industrial companies: level of awareness, diffusion and enablers of adoption*. *Virtual reality*, 26-38.

Herremans, I. M. (2016). *Stakeholder relationships, engagement, and sustainability reporting*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 417-435.

Hine, J. A. (2009). "Society is out there, organisation is in here": On the perceptions of corporate social responsibility held by different managerial groups. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 381-393.

Hofstede, G. (1984): *Culture's consequence: International differences in work-related values*, Beverley Hills, Sage.

Jaansoo, A (2019) <https://www.nispa.org/conference2020.php?cid=28&sid=2008>

Jarald, J. (2015). *The VR book: human-centered design for virtual reality*. San Rafael: Morgan & Claypool.

Johansen, T. R. (2008). Employees and the operation of accountability. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 247-263.

Jolibert, C. (2012). The influence of stakeholder engagement. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 100-111.

Klievink, B. (2013). Facilitating adoption of international information infrastructures. *Lect Notes Comput Sci*, 250-261.

Kujala, J. (2022). Stakeholder Engagement: Past, Present, and future. *Business & Society*, 1-60.

Laude, D. (2020). *Indices of stakeholder engagement*. St Gallen: Unpublished.

Legacy, C. (2010). Investigating the knowledge interface between stakeholder engagement and plan-making. *Environment and Planning*, 2705-2720.

Lewicki, R. J. (2005). *Negotiations*. Toronto: Irwin.

Linstone, H. (1975). *The Delphi method: techniques and applications*. London: Addison-Wesley.

Masood T, E. J. (2020). Adopting augmented reality in the age of industrial digitalization. *Comput Ind.*

Mather, H. (2002). Searching for the Moral Foundations of Contract Law. *The American journal of jurisprudence*, 71-83.

Miska, C. H. (2014). Reconciling different views on responsible leadership: A rationality-based approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 349-360.

Mitchell, J. R. (2022). Stakeholder engagement, knowledge problems and ethical challenges. *Journal of business ethics*, 75-94.

Mitter, H. (2019). A protocol to develop shared socio-economic pathways. *Journal of Environmental Management*.

Nalick, M. J. (2016). Corporate sociopolitical involvement: A reflection of whose preferences? *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 384-403.

Nardi, Bonnie and O'Day, Vicki L. (1999): *Information Ecologies. Using Technology with Heart*. Cambridge, Mass. and London, England: The MIT Press.

Noland, J. &. (2010). Stakeholder engagement, discourse ethics and strategic management. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 29-39.

Novoa, A. S.-S. (2018). A framework for engaging stakeholders on the management of alien species. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 286-297.

O'Riordan, L. &. (2014). Managing CSR stakeholder engagement. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121-145.

Patzer, M. (2018). The normative justification of integrative stakeholder engagement: A Habermasian view on responsible leadership. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 325-344.

Pucci, T. C. (2020). The virtuous cycle of stakeholder engagement in developing a sustainability culture: Salcheto winery. *Journal of Business Research*, 364-376.

Purnell, L. S. (2012). Stakeholder theory, fact/value dichotomy, and the normative core: How Wall Street stops the ethics conversation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 109-116.

Resnik D. B (1991) Statistics, ethics, and research: An agenda for education and reform, *Accountability in Research: Policies and Quality Assurance*, 8:1-2, 163-188

Quinn, D. P. (1995). An agent morality view of business policy of business society . *Academy of management review*, 22-42.

Sachs, S. (2021). Where do stakeholders come from? *Academy of Management Review*.

Sandberg, J. &. (2010). Grasping the logic of practice: Theorizing through practical rationality. *Academy of Management Review*, 338-360.

Scardamalia, M., & Bereiter, C. (1994). Computer support for knowledge-building communities. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 3, 265-283.

Scholz, M. (2019). The enduring potential of justi-fied hypernorms. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 317-342.

Shackleton, R. T. (2019). Stakeholder engagement in the study and management of invasive alien species. *Environmental policy*, 215-223.

Stutz, C. (2018). Facing the normative changes. *Business and society*, 98-130.

Todeschini, B. V. (2020). Collaboration practices in the fashion industry: Environmentally sustainable innovations in the. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 1-11.

UNDP. (2020). UNDP Social and Environmental Standards (SES). UNDP, 1-50.

Viglia, G. (2018). The determinants of stakeholder engagement in digital platforms. *Journal of Business Research*, 404-410.

Voparil, C. J. (2010). *The Rorty reader*. John Wiley.

Watts, Duncan J. (1999) *Small Worlds: The Dynamics of Networks and Randomness*. Princeton University Press.

Watson, R. (2020). Business-nonprofit engagement in sustainability-oriented innovation: What works for whom and why? *Journal of Business Research*, 87-98.

Wenger, E. (1998): *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*, University Press Cambridge, Cambridge, UK.

Wenger, E., McDermott, R. & Snyder, W. (2002): *Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to Managing Knowledge*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA, 2002.

Wenger, E., White N., and Smith, J.D (2009): *Digital habitats: Stewarding Technology for communities*. Portland, OR: CPSquare.

Wimmer, M. (2012). Method and tools to support stakeholder engagement in policy development: the OCOPOMO Project. *Int'l J Electron Gov Res*, 98-119.

6 APPENDICES

Appendix 1

Fig. 2 Influence/Interest Matrix (Mendelow, 1991)

Appendix 2

Figure 3. Stakeholder information that must be obtained prior to the development of a stakeholder engagement plan

Who?	<p>Which stakeholder groups and individuals are to be engaged based on the stakeholder analysis?</p> <p>Have potentially marginalized groups and individuals been identified among stakeholders?</p>
Why?	<p>Why is each stakeholder group participating (e.g., key stakeholder objectives and interests)? What are their main drivers and incentives to participate?</p>
What?	<p>What is the breadth and depth of stakeholder engagement at each stage of the project cycle?</p> <p>What decisions need to be made through stakeholder engagement?</p>
How?	<p>How will stakeholders be engaged (strategy and methods, including communications)?</p> <p>Are special measures required to ensure the inclusive participation of marginalized or disadvantaged groups?</p>
When?	<p>What is the timeline for engagement activities, and how will they be sequenced, including information disclosure?</p>
Responsibilities	<p>How have roles and responsibilities for conducting stakeholder engagement been distributed among project partners (e.g., resident mission, executing agency, consultants, NGOs)?</p> <p>What role will stakeholder representatives play?</p> <p>Are stakeholder engagement facilitators required?</p>
Resources	<p>What will the Stakeholder Engagement Plan cost and under what budget?</p>

Appendix 3

Table 3: Six steps stakeholder engagement model

ENGAGEMENT APPROACH	OVERVIEW	EXAMPLE
MONITOR	Tracking or monitoring Stakeholder positions via research or discussion with other parties	Tracking the issues of the greatest concern of selected Stakeholder groups
MESSAGE	Adapting communications scope and messaging to meet Stakeholder expectations	Creating and targeting messages to specific Stakeholders
ADVOCATE	Activities to enlist support for a specific effort or position that may have opposition or reflect an actual or perceived imbalance of power	Clarification of the position of the Project Partner in response to Stakeholder criticism
CONSULT	Soliciting explicit feedback or input on a project. Implies an expectation by the Stakeholders that the Project Partner will make concrete changes based on the consultation	Consultation with a Stakeholder advisory board on policy or process changes regarding the project's approach to a particular issue
COLLABORATE	Initiating or participating in two-way dialogue focused on mutual learning and solutions. Can include the co-creation of new ideas and approaches	Consultation with local community and political groups to determine the most mutually beneficial options
INNOVATE	Shared work on common objectives of the project and its Stakeholders. Can include co-creation, as well as co-implementation, of new ideas.	Launch of a new product or service in partnership with expert Stakeholders.

Table 4: Engagement techniques relevant for each engagement approach in XR4Human.

APPROACH	TECHNIQUE
INNOVATE COLLABORATE CONSULT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Joint venture or partnership · External advisory council · Collaboration workshop · Joint research · Stakeholder engagement summit · Focus groups · Workshop
MESSAGE ADVOCATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Sustainability report Survey/Questionnaire · Physical Hall meetings/ online seminars · Mass email or newsletter · Social media outreach · Conferences · Website · Focus groups
MONITOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Marketing campaign and tracking · Online and social media monitoring · Subscription to Stakeholder newsletter or blog

Appendix 4

Table 5: The International Association for Public Participation stakeholder engagement

ENGAGEMENT APPROACH	OVERVIEW	MAIN GOALS

INFORMING	Reaching Stakeholders via websites, fact sheets, newsletters, or allowing visitors to read project discussions and inform themselves.	The level of engagement in this form is very low and suitable to engage stakeholders with low urgency, influence, importance, or interest (Bryson, 2004)
CONSULTING	Conducting interviews, administering surveys to gather information, opening draft project documents for public comment, or using web 2.0 tools to gather ideas.	To elicit the views, interests, and any salient information, stakeholder consultations will take place. Relevant to: 3.1 Policy debate analysis, 5.2 Stakeholder consultations, and 5.3 Creation of the XR Code of Conduct
INVOLVING	Scenario building (Wimmer, 2012) engaging panels of experts such as the Delphi method (Linstone, 1975) or group model building that includes simulating policy choices, games, or role-playing (Andersen, 2007)	Have a shared experience and exchange localized or specialized knowledge, overcome “the symmetry of ignorance” (see chapter 3) to learn, create a common understanding, and identify alternative choices
COLLABORATION	Stakeholders’ advice and recommendations will be incorporated in the final decisions to a maximum extent (EU, 2014)	Improve engagement, create tight bonds with stakeholders and in the context of XR4HUMAN, co-create Interoperability Guideline and the European Code of Conduct

EMPOWERMENT	The final decision-making is in the hands of the public.	<p>Realistically, collaboration and empowerment exist within institutional and legal parameters</p> <p>Relevant to:</p> <p>6.4: Evaluation of example use cases</p> <p>7.4: Online rating repository of guidelines and recommendations for XR ethical usage</p>
-------------	--	---

Appendix 5

Table 6: Good Faith in Stakeholder Engagement Approach

Engagement approach	Overview	Example
Dialogue	Respectful exchange of ideas, emphasizing hearing claims and testing them	Establishing the stakeholders legitimacy
Negotiations	<p>Problem-solving process designed to reach a mutually acceptable decision on common concerns, and characterized by identifying issues and differences, providing needs and interests, and generating and bargaining possible settlement options (Lewicki, 2005)</p> <p>Bargaining—exchanging proposals and counter proposals</p>	Finding and establishing the common ground and best conditions for each of the parties involved in the project

<p>Totality of Conduct</p>	<p>Action matters, inherently harmless and possibly intended to improve results actions, such as cover-ups, misinformation, fact-finding, and deception can destroy even the best relationships and connections between stakeholders and corporations.</p>	<p>Ideally, intentions should coincide with actions, and if there are conflicts or obstacles to the fulfilment of agreed terms, it is easier to disclose them in advance and get back to the negotiating table on time</p>
<p>Third-Party Neutrals</p>	<p>When the actors are not successful in their engagement through negotiation, they should accept the account and/or recommendations of a third-party neutral</p>	<p>Involving a third disinterested party proves commitment to a position of good faith and helps resolve points of contention</p>

Appendix 6

Fig.7 UNEP Stakeholder Engagement plan

Appendix 7

Table 8: Steps and actions from the UNEP Stakeholder Engagement plan

STEP	DESCRIPTION
THINK	Develop an overall consideration of strategic project objectives, how these relate to stakeholders and specific issues, and how the project can undertake an initial prioritization of stakeholders and issues for further analysis.
PLAN	Create different levels of engagement, and guide the analysis of existing relationships, available resources, and organizational constraints. To learn more about specific stakeholder's representatives, and to decide on what kind of relationship should be developed with these stakeholders.
STRENGTHEN	Address questions of internal and external competencies and capacities to engage, and how it can be ensured that all key stakeholders are able to join and take part in the project effectively.
ENGAGE	Address and outline different engagement techniques, and – building on the previous steps – design an approach that suits the needs of the project-specific situation and helps to reach the goals.
EVALUATE	Follow-up on the outputs of engagement, and ensure that stakeholders feel assured regarding the quality of final outcomes and deliverables

Appendix 8 : Form fields (questions not included)

<u>REPRESENTATIVE</u>	<u>ORGANIZATION</u>
First name	Organization name
Last name	Organization type***
Gender	Verticals* ⁴
Birth date	Type of services* ⁵
Email	Number of employees* ⁶
Job title	Website URL
Position*	Phone Number
Expertise**	Town
Phone Number	State
	Country

Position	Expertise**	Organization type***	Type of services*5	Number of employees*6	Verticals*4
C-level	3D Printing	Agency / Services Studio	Assistance	1 to 9	Aeronautics
Founder / co-founder	Artificial intelligence	Association / Foundation	Awareness	10 to 49	Architecture / Construction
Management	Augmented Reality / Mixed Reality	Cluster of XR organizations or professionals	Conception / Production/ content / Capture Technology	50 to 249	Art/ Culture + Heritage
Programmer	BIM	Large company / Enterprise	Decision Making	250 and more	Automotive
Consultant / Freelance	Captation /Tracking / Volumetric Capture / Motion Capture /Mapping	Public entity	Diagnosis		Bank / Finance / Insurance
Sales / Business Strategist	Haptics	Research Centre	Discovery / POC		Cosmetics
Communication / Marketing	Holography	SME	Gaming Contents		Defence
Industry expert	iOt/Wearables	Start-up	Historical or Heritage content production		Education
3D Artist / Content Creator	Machine Learning	University	Maintenance		Electronics + Telecom
Academic / Researcher	XR-Related Tech		Marketing/Communication		Energy
Teacher / Professor / Trainer	Robotics		Medical Device		Gaming / Entertainment / Events
Student	360 Videos		Reeducation / Rehabilitation		Environment / Humanitarian / Ethics
Other	Virtual Humans / Avatars		Remote Monitoring / Alerts		Food / Agriculture
	Audio		Sales/ Retail/ Merchandising		Healthcare / Pharmaceuticals
			Teaching / Therapy / Training		Medias / New Images / Advertising
			Virtual Worlds / Social VR		Mobility / Transportation
			Research & Development/ Hardware/Software / API / SDK		Real Estate
			Manufacture		Sports
			Other		Textile
					Tourism
					Government / policy / justice

